

PACKET SATELLITE NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Packet satellite networks combine the advantages of packet switching for channel sharing with those of satellites for long-haul broadcast capability. This paper describes the packet satellite technology as developed by DARPA and demonstrated in two systems based on channels provided by INTELSAT and WESTAR satellites, respectively.

INTRODUCTION

Packet switching communication networks have been demonstrated over the past two decades to provide a robust and reliable means for computer to computer and terminal to computer communications [5, 7]. First with the Arpanet [3] and then with networks based on radio [9, 12] and cable [14], networks have been developed and demonstrated along with appropriate protocols [13] that permit not only communications between computers on the same network, but even the interconnection of different networks in a manner that is "transparent" to the end devices.

A key element in any system of networks intended to provide global communications is the appropriate use of communication satellites. Satellites provide a means for achieving long-haul communications with relatively high bandwidth. Furthermore, satellites inherently have some additional desirable properties such as broadcast/multicast capability. Again, though, the use of satellites to support the typically bursty computer communications requirements demands the development of methods for sharing their scarce communication assets.

Starting in the mid 1970's, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) began the development of a packet satellite system; a system which combines the use of packet switching techniques for channel sharing with the advantages of long haul high bandwidth common user satellite channels. This paper describes the results of that research.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Packet satellite networks have the structure shown in Figure 1. Multiple ground nodes share a

Figure 1: Packet Satellite Network Structure

single satellite channel on the uplink and a different channel on the downlink. To avoid requiring on-board processing, it is assumed that the satellite is a simple repeater; taking whatever it receives on the uplink and retransmitting it (on the different frequency) on the downlink. (This restriction will be relaxed in a system described under the Future Systems section below.) Thus, each ground site hears all transmissions from all other ground sites assuming no collision (transmission by multiple ground sites simultaneously) occurs.

In conventional satellite communications, such collisions are avoided by either assigning channels to a given ground site or, where sharing of a channel is required, dividing the channel into frequency or time slots, and assigning the slots in a way that avoids collisions. Such assignments assume that the requirement is changing slowly enough so that the assignments will allow the channel to be used efficiently. In the case of computer communications, this is often an

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unrealistic assumption, as most computer communications is quite bursty; often representing transmission of a user-typed line of text or transfer of a modest size file. Thus, it was necessary to develop a system that permitted the channel to be shared on a more dynamic basis. The development of those algorithms represents the majority of the effort involved in the DARPA packet satellite research.

Channel Sharing Algorithms

An early approach to channel sharing was the use of pure random access. Known as the ALOHA protocol [1] (Named after a system at University of Hawaii where the protocol was first developed and used), it involves the simple and elegant algorithm of transmitting whenever a packet is in the queue, and then if the transmission is not successful (as determined by either acknowledgment or other feedback), the packet is retransmitted. Several improvements have been developed over the years to the pure ALOHA protocol including disciplined ALOHA and slotted ALOHA [14]. Even with the improvements, however, the maximum throughput achievable was shown to be roughly 36% of channel capacity [11]. To satisfy the requirement of bursty computer communications where the instantaneous communication demand can vary quickly, this can often be a reasonable and effective approach.

For some environments, it is possible to improve on the achievable throughput by using available real-time channel feedback. For example, the CSMA (Carrier Sense Multiple Access) protocol [10] allows each node to sense the channel prior to transmission to determine if the channel is busy already (another node is transmitting). If it is, the node does not transmit and reschedules the transmission for a later time. A modification of CSMA, suitable for use on cable networks, uses collision detection to determine if multiple transmissions are present on the channel, and if so, each node aborts its transmission. CSMA and its variations are applicable when the propagation delay is considerably shorter than the packet duration, so that the real-time feedback is applicable to the current packet. Thus, in typical ground radio or cable network environments, CSMA or a variation thereof is often used [12, 2].

In a high-bandwidth satellite channel, however, propagation delay can typically be several times the packet duration. For example, using a 50 kbps channel and a packet duration of 1000 bits (typical numbers for packet networks and typical usage), the packet duration is 20 ms compared to a roundtrip delay for geosynchronous satellites of 270 ms. Thus, there is no real-time feedback available for nodes to use to detect whether a channel is busy or not. To support fully dynamic access, therefore, ALOHA and its variations are the protocols available.

On the other hand, certain types of computer to computer communications can involve the use of more continuous "stream" traffic. In particular, long file transfers and digitized voice represent two user requirements that can be effectively supported through less dynamic channel allocation mechanisms than individual packet by packet allocation. To support this type of usage, a protocol was

developed called Priority Oriented Demand Access (PODA) [8, 15]. In this algorithm, nodes on the network make reservations for time slots on the channel. While this results in a delay in transmission of the first packet (which is why it is not appropriate for allocation on a packet by packet basis), it results in more efficient sharing of the channel for streams (multiple packets in a row).

There are two types of scheduling algorithms that can be associated with PODA; centralized and decentralized. In the centralized algorithm, each node with traffic in its queue sends a reservation request to a centralized site, which then does the channel allocation (time slot assignment) and sends the assignment to the nodes which then transmit on their assigned time slots. In the decentralized algorithm, advantage is taken of the broadcast nature of the network by having each node run an identical scheduling algorithm based on its received reservation requests from all the nodes. Presumably (in the absence of errors), each node will calculate the same scheduling and therefore avoid conflicts. It should be noted that the centralized algorithm can be made to have reliability unaffected by loss of a given node by simply having dynamic election of the scheduler node (say by using the lowest number node that is operational). The decentralized algorithm has the disadvantage of potential mis-scheduling due to channel errors, but again this can be minimized through use of appropriate scheduling algorithms to avoid time propagation of the error.

Such a reservation scheme obviously requires a means for transmitting reservations with minimal conflicts. While it is possible (and is done in the DARPA systems) to piggy-back reservations on existing traffic flows, it is also necessary to be able to initiate new streams. Two methods have been explored for doing this. The first, called Fixed PODA (FPODA) reserves a portion of the time frames of the channel for reservations, and assigns each node a fixed slot within that reserved portion to transmit reservations. While this method works well for small numbers of ground sites, it becomes inefficient when large numbers of ground sites are being supported. To accommodate this latter case, a variation known as Contention-based PODA (CPODA) is being explored. CPODA again reserves a portion of the time frame of each channel for reservations, but does not assign each ground site a fixed slot within the reservation portion. Instead, the ground sites contend for the slots using ALOHA or a variation thereof. Thus, an arbitrary number of ground sites can be supported as long as the total transmitted reservation traffic does not exceed the throughput capability of the reservation frame.

While the two options for channel sharing (datagram packet by packet allocation and reservation oriented stream service) have been presented as alternatives, in fact it is possible to integrate both into a single packet satellite system. By dividing the time frame into three sections; datagram, stream, and reservations; and by using a dynamic algorithm to shift the time frame boundaries between the three functions (e.g. allocate all available time to datagram once the stream requirement is satisfied), both services can be accommodated in a single network. This in fact

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is what is done in the Wideband Satellite Network. Further details on these scheduling algorithms may be found in reference [15].

System Structure

A packet satellite system consists typically of three elements as shown in Figure 2; a packet

Figure 2: Node Block Diagram

processor, a satellite ground station, and an interface unit. The satellite ground station is typically a standard ground station to minimize development and maintain compatibility with other satellite ground equipment. The packet processor is the heart of the system, running all the network management and control algorithms and doing the scheduling described above. The interface unit is responsible for taking the packets and control information from the packet processor and modulating them appropriately into a signal to be transmitted from the earth station. The interface unit is also responsible for performing forward error correction which is often required to achieve a sufficiently low error rate so that error detection and retransmission schemes become efficient.

DARPA Experimental Systems

DARPA has sponsored the development of two packet satellite systems. The first uses a 64 kbps channel on INTELSAT and has ground stations in the United States, United Kingdom, Sweden (supporting Norway) and Germany [8, 16]. This system is in daily use in support of joint communication, command and control experimentation being carried out by the countries mentioned. The second system uses a 3 Mbps channel on WESTAR and has seven ground stations in the United States (with three more being installed by the end of 1984) [6]. This system is used to support experimentation in the integration of voice and data and in the use of packet switching techniques to support dynamic routing for the Defense Switched Network (DSN).

Based on the DARPA experimental work, two other activities are exploring the use of packet switching for satellites. The Navy has sponsored the development of a system using a 19.2 kbps channel on the FLTSAT to provide secure communications between ships and shore [4]. The Army is sponsoring the development of a system that uses tactical multichannel links to provide trunks

to connect various packet switched nodes. This last system, it should be pointed out, does not use the channel sharing algorithms discussed above but rather uses point to point links provided by the existing Army communication system to support a packet switched network.

Future Systems

All of the systems discussed above use fixed geosynchronous satellites to provide a fully connected broadcast network, where the satellite's only role is to rebroadcast all received signals on the channel. Another architecture currently being explored is one of multiple proliferated satellites with cross-linking. By having a large number of satellites, each with an on-board packet switch to provide dynamic routing, and by choosing orbits for the satellite that result in a relatively dense shell of satellites, a high degree of robustness and reliability can be achieved. Such a system is currently being investigated for its feasibility and cost effectiveness (based on the fact that the reliability and therefore cost of each satellite need not be as high for a proliferated satellite system as for a single satellite.)

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

An architecture has been described for the combination of packet switching and satellite communications, based on two systems developed and demonstrated by DARPA. These systems have proven themselves to be useful and effective in supporting long-haul computer communications and the integration of voice and data services. One such use is in the support of voice conferencing. Through the use of satellite (and its inherent broadcast capability) and packet switching (with its inherent ability to control access dynamically), a voice conferencing system has been developed and demonstrated. Future research will be focussing on architectures such as the proliferated satellite system that make use of onboard signal processing and on advanced services that can be provided through the use of packet satellite networks.

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